

WORK IMMERSION PROGRAM FOR ENHANCING THE COMPETENCIES OF GRADE 12 STUDENTS IN CURRICULUM EXIT PREFERENCE

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ABSTRACT

This research focuses on the work immersion program and its relationship with the competencies in the curriculum exit preference among the grade 12 students in Alabat Island National High School in the school year 2020-2021. The researcher gathered the demographic profile of the respondents in terms of age, sex, parents occupation, and family income. It also investigated the perception of the respondents on the work immersion program related variables as to school-related in terms of policies and guidelines, teachers competencies, and administrative support. As to home-based, it looked into the work immersion experiences, work environment, and immersion training activities. Respondents competencies in the curriculum exit preference were described in terms of employment, entrepreneurship, higher education/college education, and middle level skills development. Random sampling and descriptive method of research was used in this study. Out of 136 respondents, the findings of this study revealed that student perceptions on the work immersion related variables as school related in terms of policies and guidelines, teachers competencies, and administrative support are all often practiced. When it comes to work immersion program related variables as to home-based in terms of work immersion experiences, work environment, and immersion training activities are all often practiced. Students perception on the competencies in the curriculum exit preference in terms of employment, entrepreneurship, higher/college education, and middle level skills development indicate and showed that the respondents are competent and ready to enter into the world of work and pursue higher education. Further, significant relationship exists between school-related variables and home-based related variables to work immersion program on employment, higher/college education, and middle level skills development. The researcher made the following recommendations based on the findings and conclusions: Senior high school students may use the work immersion program as an avenue to what curriculum exit they will prefer after graduation. Senior high school teachers may continue to provide valuable information and training relative to the curriculum exit preference during classroom discussions and career guidance. School administrators may continue their best practices, administrative support and strict compliance to the policies and guidelines for work immersion program to sustain the better learning outcomes of senior high school graduates.

Keywords: Work Immersion Program, Curriculum Exit Preference, Competencies